

External factors that affect accuracy of ultrasonic sensor

Accuracy of the ultrasonic sensor measurements can rely on many factors but in this article, we are talking about some of the external factors that will affect to the accuracy of the sensor .

Common use of the ultrasonic sensor is distance measuring and object detecting . The Ultrasonic sensor's operating Principle is based on sound wave reflection. sensor needs to operate above the frequency of sound waves from 40KHz -400KHz. Sensors can identify the presence or absence of an objects by sending sound waves.

Figure 1 HCSR04 sensor

Detail information

- Power : 5V DC
- current : 2mA
- Effectual angle : 15 degree
- Ranging distance : 2cm – 400 cm
- Resolution : 0.3 cm

A receiver transmitter and a control circuit are included in each HC-SR04 module.

External factors that affect.

1. Temperature

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma RT}{\rho V}} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma RT}{M}}$$

$$v \propto \sqrt{T}$$

$$v_t = (332 + 0.61 t) \text{ m/s}$$

The speed of sound is directly proportional to temperature, meaning that as the temperature rises, so does the speed of sound. We may deduce from the preceding equation that as temperature rises, the speed of sound increases by a factor of 0.61.

2. Density

The impact of density on speed of sound is negative, for example as density increases, sound speed decreases, will affect the accuracy of distance measurement units.

3. Humidity

When the quantity of water molecules in the air grows, the molar mass of the air decreases, and the speed of sound increases, implying that the speed of sound is proportional to the number of water molecules in the air.

4. Surface properties

Smooth surfaces give the best accurate results with ultrasonic sensor . there can be sound absorbing materials as well ex (textiles, cottons)

conclusion

when we are designing a system, we must consider all the affecting factors ,first then only we will get the most accurate system.

Reference

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